

CONDITIONS OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHIATRIC PATHOLOGIES.

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Relevance. Issues of combined diseases of the oral cavity (OR) and internal organs occupy a prominent place in dentistry, as they make it possible to reflect the essence of the genesis of many dependent diseases of the oral cavity and outline ways to develop complex preventive measures. Therefore, it is often noted that tissue lesions in the PR are, in most cases, the first clinical signs of disorders in diseases of the neuroendocrine, hematopoietic, digestive, cardiovascular systems (CVS), etc.

Key words: neuropsychiatric diseases, caries and its complications, periodontal tissues, temporomandibular joint, occlusion.

The dependence of the occurrence of a pathological situation in PR on the general condition of the body is beyond doubt, while the incidence of caries, periodontitis and pathologies of the high-mandibular joints in a number of somatic diseases, including those exposed to harmful factors on the human body, has been proven. In the formation of the pathological process, a number of authors see the possible pathogenetic role of dysfunction of the autonomic nervous system (ANS) and the central nervous system (CNS). The relationship between the occurrence of wedge-shaped dental defects and diseases of the central nervous system has been noted. Also, the state of the dental system (DS) and the provision of comprehensive dental care to mentally ill people is a poorly studied issue. In the formation of the pathological process, a number of authors see the possible pathogenetic role of dysfunction of the autonomic nervous system (ANS) and the central nervous system (CNS). The relationship between the occurrence of wedge-shaped dental defects and diseases of the central nervous system has been noted. Also, the state of the dental system (DS) and the provision of comprehensive dental care to mentally ill people is a poorly studied issue.

Conclusion. Thus, the dental status of patients with dental caries is characterized by a high intensity of dental caries ($20.67 \pm 0.82^*$); including; with diagnoses of schizophrenia - $21.52 \pm 0.98^*$; epilepsy - $22.86 \pm 0.94^*$; oligophrenia - $19.64 \pm 0.78^*$; - other mental illnesses - $18.66 \pm 0.98^*$; at the same time, among the examined K/G - 11.44 ± 0.62 due to the large number of carious and extracted teeth and the high need for prosthetics from 8.2 ± 0.48 to 9.4 ± 1.4 of which the need for prosthetics is more than three teeth one jaw from 4.8 ± 0.44 to

5.8±0.80*; At the same time, the need for more than 3 teeth is equal to that of K/G. Also, a correlation analysis between the values of GC parameters, PR hygiene and the intensity of damage to hard dental tissues and periodontal tissues revealed varying degrees of relationship between these parameters.

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